

GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF COIR INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

It is nostalgic to reminisce the good old days when every household in India, especially in the South had its own coir rope cots, while chit chatting in the spacious verandas. Be it matting's, coir plant pots, the natural fibre - coir was in vogue. His also had a huge negative impact on traditional industries. Needless to say, the melancholy underscores the relevance of the eco-friendly fibre in creation of sustainable environment while reinstating its importance as the fibre of future today. Kerala is popularly known as the God's own country alone accounts for 61% of total coconut production and 85% of total coir products. Coir has come a long way from its small beginnings in the State of Kerala, centuries back. Coir product making is an important cottage industry, contributing significantly to the economy of the major coconut growing states such as Kerala, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. China is the major importer for India accounting the market share of nearly 37.34 per cent of India's export. This article analyses the performance of Coir Industries in terms of Coir Fibre Production in India during ten years and current financial year. Growth in production of coir products during 2010-2011 to 2019-2020, Exports of Coir during Last ten Years and current financial year. The compound growth in volume is negative for the export of coir pith and handloom mats, rubberized and coir yarn etc; USA continues to be the largest importer of the Indian coir and coir products followed china, Netherland, South Korea and England. SPSS is the tool used to analyze the data.

Keywords: Coir, Coir Board, Coir Export, Coir Pith, Employment, Export

Introduction

Coir is the only natural fibre that does not get cultivated solely to extract the coir whereas jute and sisal are grown only to produce the fibres and in turn, the spun and woven products. Fibres like jute, sisal, cotton etc are derived from short cropping plants whereas coir originates from the near perennial coconut palm. This is perhaps the only tree, which has a systematic recorded history dating back to nearly 3000 years before the birth of Christ. Botanists say that the coconut was domesticated in Neolithic, Stone Age,

times. When the 1st Ice Age has frozen much of the waters of the world reducing the distance between the islands and continents, seafaring tribes found it easy to move between landmasses. In Indian mythology, it is believed that this is one of the five wish giving trees that emerged after the churning of the might oceans by the Gods. According to the Indian Coconut Committee's "History and Home of Coconut" published in September 1954, the coconut palm originated in Sri Lanka. In another view, the coconuts drifted in the sea from Polynesia and found new homes in many parts of the world. According to early Greek Chronicles, it was Megasthenes, Ambassador of the Seleucid Emperor, who told the Indian King, Chandra Gupta about the Coconut Palm, he found in Sri Lanka in 300 BC. Arab writers of 11th century AD referred to the uses of coir as ships cables, fenders and rigging. "Marco Polo's celebrated travelogue of the 12th century mentioned on the uses to which coir fibre and mats were put in use in the sailing vessels of Arabs.

Coir Industry in India

Coir is a coarse fibre extracted from husk, the fibrous outer shell of coconut. Ropes and cordage, made out of coconut fibre have been in use from ancient times. Indian navigators, who sailed the seas to Malaya, Java, China and to the Gulf of Arabia centuries ago, had been using coir as their ship's cables. Matting and other floor coverings, was started in India on a factory basis, over a hundred and fifty years ago when the first factory was set up in Alappuzha in 1859. Coir industry is an agro-based traditional industry, which originated in the State of Kerala and proliferated to the other coconut producing states like Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Assam, Tripura, etc. It is an export oriented industry having potential to enhance exports by value addition through technological interventions. Coir products have great demand in the domestic markets as well as in foreign markets. But coir industry has some practical problems for which this industry could not develop to its full potential. Subrata Sarkar (2012 & 2013) the significance of economic environment has a greater impact on the trends of coir exports than industry-specific interventions. Roshni Narendran (2014), the industry employs vast numbers of disempowered social sections, mostly of the lower castes and outcastes, an overwhelming majority of them are women. Coir and coir products make good progress in the domestic as well as international market because of their unique qualities of durability, bio-degradability and eco-friendliness. Mohanasundaram et al (2015) it is suggested that the government may enforce labour welfare measures such as provident fund and medical facilities for coir workers. The Government may establish a separate department to safeguard the welfare of the coir industry workers. Mohanraj et al (2017) Coir pith used to various form of products central European countries. Export promotion council of India and coir board of MSME is gave a full support to increase the export of coir products. Praveenkumar (2017). According to a recent press release from the Ministry of MSMEs, export of coir and coir products in 2019-20 was worth ₹ 2,757.9 crore, which was ₹ 30 crore higher

than the previous year. Export of coir pith, tufted mats, geo textiles, coir rugs, and carpets registered growth in terms of value and volume. Products such as coir yarn, handloom mats, rubberized coir, and power loom matting showed decline in volume, but increase in value. Coir pith with export earnings of ₹ 1,349.63 crore constituted 49 % of the total export of coir products from the country last financial year. Value added products constituted 33 %. Soundaiya Priya (2016). They are being usually effectively used for improving soil behaviors, preventing soil erosion, and in helping consolidation of soil. Coir is a 100% organic and bio-degradable fiber which has great water absorbency and has a definite edge over synthetic geotextiles, in the environmental aspect and issues. (Poornimadevi (2017)). USA continues to be the largest importer of the Indian coir and coir products followed by UK, Australia, France, Netherland, Italy, Germany and Spain. Anu. (2018). Beginning in 1859 when the Irish American named James darragh started the first coir factory drags-small a large scale production cum commercial factory in Aleph over the years the industry has grown to secure its place of prestige in the industrial map of India with international importance. Padmanaban(2018) in the coir sector there is no regular job or income for employees. As I don't know any other job, I am forced to stick to the sector to make a living. In recent years, I have shifted units several times due to lack of work. Compared to other sectors, coir workers get minuscule salary -- that too irregularly. Sam paul. A (2019). The government's aim is to bring the coir industry back to its glory, and that its efforts are getting good response from workers and the cooperative sector. Staff report (2020) In this study analysis of Performance Regarding Manufacturing of Coir in MSMEs by analyzing their Production of coir, Exports of Coir, Growth in production of coir products. Manjusmita Dash (2021).

SCHEMES FOR COIR INDUSTRY

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Coir Board has been participating in the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, a flagship program of the Central Government, by making significant contributions. The Board has been implementing its Action Plan containing several action points approved for the year 2020-2021.

SCHEMES IMPLEMENTED BY COIR BOARD

Coir Vikas Yojana (CVY)

Coir Board has been implementing various schemes/programmes for the overall growth and development of coir Industry in the country. The component schemes/programmes implemented under the umbrella Scheme, Coir Vikas Yojana are the following:

(i) Science & Technology (S & T)

Innovative R&D on coir is carried out under the Coir Board by the two research institutes; the Central Coir Research Institute (CCRI), Kalavoor and Central Institute of Coir Technology (CICT), Bangalore on the following areas.

- i. Modernization of Production Processes in coir sector.
- ii. Development of Machinery & Equipment.
- iii. Product Development & Diversification.
- iv. Development of Environment Friendly Technology.
- v. Technology transfer, Incubation, Testing & Service facilities.

During the year under report, the following achievements are made under the institutes: NRIDA has issued order for use of coir geotextiles under new material/new technology category and allocated 5% of the length of rural roads under PMGSY III in Seven States. Developed a brush using the waste cut bits of PVC/ rubber tufted coir mats on a wooden mop with replaceable brush portion at the bottom. These types of brushes can be useful for cleaning carpets, matting and door mats, which can be used for different cleaning purposes at a low cost during this pandemic condition.

Functions of Coir Board

“The functions of the Coir Board for the development of coir industry, inter-alia, include:

1. Promoting exports of coir yarn and coir products and carrying on propaganda for that purpose.
2. Regulating under the supervision of the Central Government the production of husks, coir yarn and coir products by registering coir spindles and looms for manufacturing coir products as also manufacturers of coir products.
3. Undertaking, assisting or encouraging scientific, technological and economic research and maintaining and assisting in the maintenance of one or more research institutes;
4. Collecting statistics from manufacturers of and dealers in coir products and from other persons as may be prescribed, on any matter relating to the coir industry and the publication of statistics so collected.
5. Fixing grade standards are arranged when necessary for inspection of fibre, coir yarn and coir products.
6. Improving the marketing of coconut husk, coir fibre, coir yarn and coir products in India and elsewhere and preventing unfair competitions;
7. Setting up or assisting in the setup of factories for the producers of coir products with the aid of power.
8. Promoting co-operative organization among producers of husks, coir fibre and coir yarn and manufactures of coir products.

9. Ensuring remunerative return to producers of husks coir fibre and coir yarn and manufacturers of coir products;
10. Advising on all matters relating to the development of the coir industry.”¹

Literature Review

Senthilkumar.R (2015) in his study recorded that even though Coir Industries in India are facing lot of problems, it has various opportunities for further growth and development. The coir industry has wide future prospects in terms of availability of coconut husks, providing employment, reducing unemployment, generating income, alleviating poverty, improving the standard of living of the people, creating great demand in both domestic as well as international markets, developing entrepreneurship and promoting the country's economy. He concluded that the Government of India, through Coir Board, can promote the coir industry in terms of solving the various problems faced by the coir industry in India and opening the gateway for future prospects.

Praveenkumar and Vinayagamoorthi (2017) in their article entitled “A Study on Export Performance of Coir Industry in India” observed that China is the major importer of Indian coir products. Coir pith is used in various forms of products in central European countries. Export promotion council of India and coir board of MSME give full support to increase the export of coir products and also governments have many plans to develop the industry. It was also observed that the people involved in the industry are lacking awareness on the devolvement, promotional and subsidy schemes available for coir industry.

VennilaashreeS., (2018) in his research paper focuses on the government's support to the coir board for undertaking the various activities related with coir industry. Data shows the plan expenditure and allocation of funds. The research paper further highlights the production of coir in India of last six years and employment opportunities.

Venkatesh and Kumaran (2019) in their article entitled “Export Performance of Coir Industry in India” found that the export performance of Handloom Mats, Power loom Mats, Rubberized Coir and Tufted Mats have increased gradually after globalization. The export performance of other coir products showed a wavering trend except the export of Curled Coir which shows a decreasing trend. The export performance of Handloom Mats, Power loom Mats, Rubberized Coir and Tufted Mats is satisfactory. This trend should be continued in the future also. The authors also suggested that state government as well as the Coir Board should encourage the entrepreneurs to go for the manufacture of value-added coir products and the Self-help groups which have a strong presence in the study area may be motivated and helped to undertake the manufacturing of traditional coir products like mats, mattresses, coir ropes, carpets and

¹Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2020-2021

innovative coir products like coir composites, coco-lawn, coir bricks and coir geotextiles.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

For the critical analysis on the performance of coir industry in India, five performance indicators such as growth, production, employments, export, and import. The objectives framed for the present study are: to trace the origin, growth and development of coir industry at the national and state levels; to evaluate the role of coir board and MSME in developing coir industry; to analyse the Production of Coir and Coir products in India; to analyse the performance of coir industry with reference to exports and Imports; to analyse the number of persons employed in Coir Industries in India; to estimate the Export of Coir from India; and to offer suggestions for improving the overall performance of coir industry based on the findings of the study.

Data

This study is made based on Secondary data. Secondary data relating to the study were collected from Annual Reports, Journals and Websites.

Research Design

This study is Descriptive and Analytical in nature and hence Descriptive Research Design has been used.

Period of the Study

This study analyses the performance of Coir industries in India during ten years from 2010-2011 to 2019-2020. The data relating to Coir fibre production, Production of Coir products, Trends of Employment in Coir Industry, Export of coir products and Importers of Coir products from India country wise export, and port wise export were collected for this period

Type of Data and Data Collection

This study is made based on Secondary data. Secondary data relating to the study were collected from Annual Reports, Journals and coir board and Ministry of MSME Websites.

Framework of Analysis

The following statistical tools have been used in this article for analyzing the performance of Coir industries in India. Simple Percentage Analysis, Compound Annual Growth Rate, and Linear Trend Analysis

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1 State-wise Coir Units Registered with Coir Board

S.No.	State	No of Units	Percentage
1	Kerala	9206	55.43
2	Tamil Nadu	4463	26.87
3	Andrapradesh	998	06.00
4	Odisha	933	05.61
5	Karanadka	724	04.35
6	West Bengal	59	00.35
7	North East Region	56	00.33
8	Mahatastra	53	03.17
9	Puduchary	31	00.18
10	New Delhi	17	00.10
11	Other States	67	00.40
	TOTAL	16607	100.00

Source: https://dashboard.msme.gov.in/coir_product_wise.aspx

The Table 1 shows that the states of Kerala and Tamil Nadu have the maximum number of coir units in India. The highest number of units (9206) is found in Kerala and the lowest in New Delhi (17). Kerala state, the “Home of Coir in India”, continues to enjoy the leading position till date. The state of Kerala stands with the largest share of 55.43 per cent followed by Tamil Nadu with 26.87 per cent as on 31st March 2020.

Table 2 Growth in production of coir products during 2018-19 to 2020-2021

S.No	Item	2018-19 (Qty in MT)	2019-20 (Qty in MT)	2020-21 (Qty in MT)	Mean	S.D	C.V	ACGR
1	Coir fibre	7,49,600	7,41,000	7,10,000	733533	17007	0.023	-2.79
2	Coir yarn	4,49,800	4,46,000	4,27,300	441033	9834	0.022	-2.70
3	Coir products	2,96,800	2,94,200	2,81,900	290967	6498	0.022	-2.70
4	Coir Rope	90,000	89,200	85,500	88233	1960	0.022	-2.70
5	Curled Coir	89,900	88,800	85,100	87933	2053	0.023	-2.81
6	Rubberized coir	89,100	89,500	90,700	89767	680	0.008	0.60

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2020-2021.

Table No. 2 clearly reveals the status of production of coir products from the financial year 2018-2019 to 2019-2020. In all the product categories for all the three

financial years there is improvement in production. Production of all coir products have seen great improvement in the year 2018-19 compared to the next financial year 2019-2020. The Compound Annual Growth Rate of all Coir products during the study period is similar. The CAGR of Coir fibre, Coir Yarn and Coir Products are -2.79%, -2.70% Coir rope is 1-2.70%, Curled coir is -2.81%% and only positive growth rate of Rubberized coir is 0.60%.

Table3
STATE WISE TRENDS OF EMPLOYMENT IN COIR INDUSTRY
(2014-2020 Estimated March 2020)

S.No	State	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	CAGR
1	Kerala	4,70,788	4,72,100	4,72,961	4,74,590	4,75,077	4,75,750	0.17
2	Tamil Nadu	1,25,937	1,27,420	1,29,803	1,30,862	1,32,443	1,33,375	0.96
3	Karnataka	0,338	30,440	30,872	31,365	31,365	31,580	0.67
4	Andhra Pradesh	2,946	53,825	54,477	4,670	55,455	55,585	0.81
5	Odisha	7,210	7,535	17,760	8,135	8,421	8,490	1.2
6	Others	0,542	0,650	20,876	0,965	1,031	21,200	0.53

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2019-2020.

Table 3 despite that Kerala and Tamil Nadu are the centers of the development of coir and major unit's works there so higher employment is seen in the both states. Highest employment is seen in the Kerala in the year 2019-20 which is 475750. In other states like Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Odisha it is comparatively less. The Compound Annual Growth Rate indicates that the rate of Increase in number of people employed in Coir Industries during the study period is meager. Odisha registered the highest CAGR of 1.2% and interestingly Kerala registered the lowest CAGR of 0.17%

MAJOR IMPORTERS OF COIR FROM INDIA

United States of America, China, Netherlands, South Korea, and England are the major importers of coir products from India. India is one of the major quality suppliers of coir products to world countries. There is great demand for India's coir products in world market. Product innovation, modification and the use of new technology have provided strong marketing strength to Indian coir exporters.

Table 4
The top 5 Coir Importing Countries from India during 2020-21
(as on November 2020)

Sl. No.	Country	Quantity (Tonnes)	Percentage (%)	Value (Rs. in Lakhs)	Percentage (%)
1	USA	125482.57	17.37	68315.78	30.30
2	China	269752.82	37.34	50923.26	22.58

3	Netherlands	61276.17	8.48	17904.54	7.94
4	South Korea	49079.33	6.79	11950.18	5.30
5	UK	18738.59	2.59	9087.70	4.03

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2020-2021

Table 4 indicates that United States of America is the top buyer of coir products from India buying our exportable items for 30.30% of value. China is in the second position buying 37.74% of quantity for 22.58% of value. Netherlands, South Korea and England are in the next three positions with 8.48%, 6.79 % and 2.59% of quantity import from India.

Table 5
Coir fibre Production and Exports in India during last Five years and current financial year (2015-2016 to 2020-2021)

S. No	Year	Production (Quantity (Metric Ton)	Exports (Quantity) (Metric Ton)
1	2015-2016	5,49,300	7,52,020
2	2016-2017	5,56,900	9,57,045
3	2017-2018	5,59,400	10,16,564
4	2018-2019	7,49,600	9,64,046
5	2019-2020	7,41,000	9,88,996
6	2020-2021	7,10,000	10,00,000
TOTAL		38,66,200	56,78,671
MEAN		644367	946445
S.D		90025	89273
C.V		0.140	0.094
ACGR		4.37%	4.86%

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2020-2021.

Till March (estimate) 2021 the production of coir fibre was 710000metric ton. The production also goes steadily increasing. According to the data in the year 2018-19 there was highest production with 749600 metric ton. From the year 2015 to 2019 the coir production was stable and there was no major jump however, in the year 2019- 20 the major jump is seen in the production of coir which is 741000. Majority of the coir products manufactured in India are exported by the country. Coir is one of the Foreign Exchange earners for the nation. India's export of coir has been increasing constantly quantity wise from the year 2015-16 to 2020-21. Even though it has seen a slight decrease in the quantity of export during the year 2018-19 and 2019-20 it showed increase according to value of export.

Table 6 Growth of Coir Products in India

Products Name	Curled Coir	Coir Fibre	Coir Rugs	Coir Pith	Coir Rope	Coir Other Sorts	Coir Yarn	Geo-Textiles	Handloom Matting	Powerloom Matting	Rubberised Coir	Powerloom Mats	Handloom Mats	Tufted Mats	Total
2010-11	1056.52	12148.6	826.22	14829	86.72	35.84	2685.34	1823.34	1244.72	0	476.89	0	21525.8	23968.4	80707.08
2011-12	3171.3	20324	185.55	22150.7	340.99	68.75	3140.7	2433.12	1582.83	0	549.8	24.56	23545	27745.3	105262.54
2012-13	2112.46	20707.7	133.37	24727.6	282.41	39.33	2387.22	2628.74	1702.76	0	495.02	3.15	22810.1	33572.9	111602.74
2013-14	2947.93	32878.1	105.99	34173.2	390.17	163.13	2848.26	3503.78	3353.91	0	1560.76	278.36	23623.8	41776.4	147603.84
2014-15	3732	41923.3	146.1	43295.2	391.92	85.79	3000.89	3270.28	1835.28	43.93	1410.88	225.25	23946.9	39726	163033.77
2015-16	68808.56	44316	41767.1	22280	3531.72	2820.82	2510.07	1968.78	971.74	282.5	94.79	396.61	367.35	26.48	190142.52
2016-17	90539.11	48442.8	53913.6	21316.3	4481.04	2948.32	2419.3	1535.25	1295.64	271.92	416.59	388.5	196.38	0	228154.82
2017-18	101846.82	49591.4	70177.9	18614	3996.59	2457.66	2316.26	1394.79	1388.64	269.58	498.29	401.72	57.75	216.49	253227.84
2018-19	123208.48	52225	60164.1	21911	5972.56	2642.23	3137.02	1436.08	1029.58	243.96	361.58	439.79	15.89	17.22	272804.57
2019-20	134962.94	56344.1	49842.6	19630.1	6389.45	2301.22	2681.57	1366.41	786.82	483.82	476.93	466.03	49.65	8.53	275790.15
Mean	53238.6	37890.1	27726.3	24292.7	2586.4	1356.3	2712.7	2136.1	1519.2	159.6	634.2	262.4	11613.9	16705.8	182833.0
Std Dev	56169.2	15432.4	29802.0	8337.5	2552.5	1358.6	308.5	789.3	724.3	172.3	467.7	188.7	12114.9	18269.8	72228.5
Cov	1.06	0.41	1.07	0.34	0.99	1.00	0.11	0.37	0.48	1.08	0.74	0.72	1.04	1.09	0.40
CAGR	85.37	17.07	123.97	-0.64	63.89	78.77	-0.51	-7.26	-6.82	39.08	-5.63	59.12	-60.72	-64.51	15.15
t value	7.15	6.91	3.93	-0.18	7.82	5.51	-0.39	-2.38	-1.76	2.28	-0.67	2.86	-6.36	-4.59	15.29
p value	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.862	0.000	0.001	0.708	0.045	0.116	0.085	0.525	0.024	0.000	0.003	0.000
Sig/NS	SIG	SIG	SIG	NS	SIG	SIG	NS	SIG	NS	NS	NS	SIG	SIG	SIG	SIG
Expected Growth in 2020-21	250180.1	65960.2	111633.2	19505.3	10471.4	4113.9	2668.0	1267.2	733.2	672.9	450.1	741.5	19.5	3.0	317585.1

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises- Annual Report 2020-2021

Table 6 shows that Export of Curled coir and Coir fibre has been increased from the Rs. 1056.52 lakhs and Rs.12148.55 lakhs in 2010-2011 to Rs 13492.94 lakhs and Rs.56344.14 lakhs in 2019- 2020 with the Compound Growth Rate of 85.37 per cent and 17.07 per cent with the mean value is Rs.53238.6 and Rs. 37890.1 respectively . The compound growth rate is negative for the segments like Coir pith (0.64 per cent), Coir yarn (0.51 per cent), Geo-textiles (-7.16 per cent) Handloom mating (-6.82 per cent), Rubberized coir (-5.63 per cent), Handloom mats (-60.82 per cent), and Tufted mats (-64.51 per cent), during the last year of the period Coir Rugs (123.97 per cent), and Coir Rope (63.89 per cent , Coir other sorts (78.77 per cent), Power loom matting(39.08 per cent) and Power loom mats (59.12 per cent) showing a significant growth.

Conclusion

There is an opportunity to grow the coir products in India as per the data of the study period (2010-11 to 2019-20). The handloom sector has not been getting the growth, it seems to be a sick. It should be regenerated to form the growth with help of subsidies. The real rural development is taking place while concentrating in the coir products in India. The common people are involved in the business as many as hamlets of India are undergone in the affordable and simple tiny business. Hence, the India is an agricultural based country and most of the people are living in rural villages, the coir industrial production are done in rural villages, the employment opportunities are large in coir production. The government of India should give the chances of this coir production to village people with subsidy. Most of the Indian corporates are fetching this type of business to spoil the village people livelihood. The government of India is very famous for assisting the financial helps to the corporate sector. The coir production should not tie the neck of village people who are manufacturing the coir products. The responsibility of the nation is to assure the eradication of poverty in rural.

Managerial Implications

To make them fully informed on the current scenario in the coir industry and to provide them a bridge to discuss the day-to-day problems confronting their coir units. The District Industrial Centre and non-governmental organizations have an accountability to play in the coir production, and re-processing and export. To facilitate the manufacturer, the government should come forward and stream line the India as well as international coir industry market structure. In upcoming there are several opportunities in international market for value added products so that the coir board and related organization like as MSME should come forward Promote the coir industry in India . To promote the usage of coir products which are eco-friendly in nature and therefore most coir products producing state governments which ban the usage of plastic products

in them beyond the limited jurisdiction? To take necessary steps more financial assistances and incentive term loan like as (short term, medium terms and long term) are anticipated for value added product of coir manufacturing process so the government has to avail ease loan procedure. Entrepreneur development program should arrange for coir oriented entrepreneurs to make use of updated new technologies and e-commerce platform, customer Relationship Management, encouraged participating in Consumer Exhibitions, reprocessing and quality enhancement in production. New coir product machine invented for reducing the time to process coir and its manufacturing.

Limitation of the Study and Scope for Further Research

The study covers 10 years only ranging from 2010-2015 to 2015-2020 and it does not include data taken before periods. In this study primary data are not used. It depends only upon secondary data.

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